

Supporting Information

Octapod-shaped colloidal nanocrystals of cadmium chalcogenides *via* “one-pot” cation exchange and seeded growth

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1 Chemicals. Copper chloride (CuCl, 99.999%), trioctylphosphine oxide (TOPO, 99%), trioctylphosphine (TOP, 97%), tellurium (Te 99.999%), and selenium (Te 99.99%) were purchased from Strem Chemicals. Sulfur (S 99.98) Oleylamine (OLAM, 70%), oleic acid (OLAC, 90%) and 1-octadecene (ODE, 90%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Octadecylphosphonic acid (ODPA) and hexylphosphonic acid (HPA) were purchased from Polycarbon Industries. Anhydrous ethanol, toluene and chloroform were purchased from Carlo Erba reagents. All chemicals were used as received.

2 Synthesis of Cu_{2-x}Se seeds. Anhydrous CuCl (0.099 g, 1 mmol) was first added to a mixture of 5 ml of oleylamine and 5 ml of 1-octadecene (ODE) in a reaction flask. After pumping to vacuum for 1 h at 80 °C using a standard Schlenk line, the reaction mixture was put under constant nitrogen flow. The temperature was then set to 300°C. A solution of Se in oleylamine was freshly prepared by mixing 0.039 g of Se (0.5 mmol) with 3 ml of oleylamine. The solution was heated to 150°C under vacuum using a standard Schlenk line for 1h and later the line was switched to nitrogen flow and the temperature was raised to 230 °C and kept there for 1h in order to fully dissolve Selenium. This mixture was then cooled down to 100 °C. The solution was kept at this temperature and transferred into a glass syringe equipped with a large needle (12 gauge external diameter) and injected quickly into the flask. After injection, the temperature of the reaction mixture dropped to 280 °C, and it was allowed to recover to the pre-injection value. The overall reaction time after injection was 15 min, after which the flask was rapidly cooled to room temperature. Once at room temperature, 5 ml of toluene was added to the reaction mixture, and the resulting solution was transferred into a vial under nitrogen flow, and the vial was then stored inside a glove box. This solution was then washed by repeated precipitations (via addition of ethanol) and re-dissolution in toluene. After the last washing step, the Cu_{2-x}Se was dissolved in 3 ml of toluene.

3 Growth of CdS, CdSe and CdTe multipods. The synthesis of the multipods was carried out via a seeded growth approach. Briefly, a solution was prepared which contained the chalcogenide source dissolved in TOP (see table 1 for details) and previously synthesized Cu_{2-x}Se seeds, the latter in a known concentration (see section 5). This solution was injected into a reaction flask containing a mixture of surfactants (3g TOPO, 80mg HPA, 290 mg ODP) and

60mg of CdO heated at a specified temperature. After the injection, the resulting solution was allowed to recover at the pre-injection temperature for 7 minutes, after which it was cooled to room temperature (see table 1 for details). This solution was then washed by repeated precipitations (via addition of methanol) and re-dissolution in toluene. After the last washing step, the multipods were dissolved in 5 ml of toluene. The as-synthesized multipods were stored under nitrogen inside glove box.

Table S1) Summary of the parameters involved in the syntheses of the nanocrystals reported in this work.

	CdSe/CdS	CdSe/CdSe	CdSe/CdTe
Cu _{2-x} Se /(mol)	0.3*10 ⁻⁹ M	0.3*10 ⁻⁹ M	0.3*10 ⁻⁹ M
Precursor solution ^{a)}	S-TOP 0.5g	Se-TOP 0.5g	Te-TOP 0.1g
T _(injection) /(°C)	320-380	300-350	280-320
Grow time/ (min)	7	7	7

a) Solution concentrations: S-TOP=32mg/ml, Se-TOP=12mg/ml, Te-TOP 10wt%

4 Control syntheses

4.1 Cu_{2-x}Se seeds

Test reactions relied on controlling the evolution of the octapods over the time, starting from well defined Cu_{2-x}Se (Fig.S1 a) and b)) seeds which were injected into the reaction flask.

a)

b)

Figure S1 a) TEM image of Cu_{2-x}Se seeds b) XRD pattern of Cu_{2-x}Se seeds and bulk reflexes of berzelianite.

4.1 Rapid Ion exchange from Cu_{2-x}S to CdSe

One control experiment was to inject only the Cu_{2-x}S in TOP into the reaction flask which contained a cadmium alkylphosphonate (hexylphosphonate and octadecylphosphonate) in trioctylphosphine oxide (TOPO) heated to 350°C (without TOP-S,Se or Te precursors) and to keep the resulting solution under these conditions for 1 min to 7 min (Several test reactions were carried out and the results suggest that the cation exchange reaction is complete after 1 min and a longer reaction time does not significantly influence the final product). The solution was washed by repeated precipitations (via addition of ethanol) and re-dissolution in toluene. After the last washing step, the particles were dissolved in 2 ml of TOP. The obtained 15-20nm nanocrystals (Fig.S2a) were relatively uniform and the sample has a narrow particle size distribution. Furthermore, XRD analysis confirmed that the final product was sphalerite CdSe (Fig.S2b)

a)

FigureS1a) TEM image of sphalerite CdSe nanoparticles synthesized at 350°C via cation exchange starting from Cu_{2-x}S

b)

Figure S2b) XRD pattern of the sphalerite CdSe nanoparticles. The nanocrystals were synthesized at 350°C via cation exchange starting from Cu_{2-x}Se

4.2 “Two-Pot” synthesis of octapods.

Sphalerite CdSe nanocrystals, as obtained from cation exchange reaction described in the previous section, were dispersed in TOP and the concentration of the final solution was determined by building a structural model of the nanocrystal with the same geometrical parameters as determined by TEM and elemental analysis (section 5). For the “two-pot” synthesis the same amount of sphalerite CdSe seeds was used as of the Cu_{2-x}Se seeds in case of the “one-pot” synthesis ($0.3 \cdot 10^{-9}$ M). The as prepared seeds were mixed with TOP-(S,Se or Te) (same amount like in the reaction with Cu_{2-x}Se seeds). The mixture was injected into the reaction flask containing a mixture of surfactants (3g TOPO, 80mg HPA, 290 mg ODPA) and 60mg of CdO as in the case of the one-pot synthesis described previously in the report. As a result (Fig S3) uniform octapods were obtained.

Figure S3 TEM image of CdSe core/CdS arms octapods via a “two-pot” approach

4.3 Comparison of the absorption and emission spectra of the “one-pot” and “two-pot” synthesis

Figure S4. Left: absorption (black) and emission (red) spectrum of CdSe(core)/CdS(arms) octapods synthesized from Cu_{2-x}Se seeds. Right: absorption (black) and emission (red) spectrum of CdSe(core)/CdS(arms) octapods synthesized from CdSe seeds (obtained by cation exchange).

Figure S4 shows that there is no significant difference in the absorption and emission spectra of the octapods obtained by the “one-pot” and the “two-pot” routes of the octapod synthesis.

Together with the elemental analysis (see below) this is also a strong hint that there is no Cu doping in the final structure when Cu_{2-x}Se seeds are used.

4.4 Temporal evolution of octapods

4.4.1 CdSe core –CdS arms: Figure 4 shows the evolution of octapod with time. Aliquots were taken after 1, 3, 5 and 7 min of reaction at 350°C .

Figure S5. TEM micrographs of aliquots of CdSe core/CdS arms octapods: a) 1min after injection b) 3 min after injection c) 5 min after injection d) final product obtained after 7 min

The TEM micrographs show the evaluation of the CdSe/CdS octapods over the time. In this particular system after one minute (Fig. S5a) arms could not be observed yet, however particles

were already sphalerite CdSe as it was confirmed by previous tests. After 3 minutes of the reaction (Figure S5b) the octapods were uniform and the length of the arms was already between 10-15 nm, whereas after 5 minutes of the reaction (Fig.S5c) the length of the arms was already doubled (25 nm). The final product after 7 minutes of the reaction (Fig S5d) consisted of octapods with an average arms length between 30-40 nm.

4.4.2 CdSe core/CdSe arms: Figure 5 shows evolution of the octapods with time, aliquots were taken after 1, 3, 5 and 7 min of reaction at 320°C.

Figure S6. TEM micrographs of aliquots of CdSe cores/CdSe arms octapods: a) 1 min

after injection b) 3 min after injection c) 5 min after injection d) final product obtained after 7 min

The growth kinetics of CdSe/CdSe octapods was much faster than the growth kinetics of the CdSe/CdS octapods and just after one minute (Fig.S6a) small tips appeared which were later on transformed into the arms of the octapods. Figure S6b shows that after 3 minutes of the reaction the arms were around 15 nm long and after 5 min of the growth (Fig.S6c) the octapods arms reached around 20 nm. At this moment the reaction was almost finished since after 7 minutes of the reaction (Fig.5d) no significant difference in the arms length was observed. The final octapods had usually arms with a length between 20 and 25 nm.

4.4.3 CdSe core/CdTe arms: Figure 6 shows the evolution of octapods with time. Aliquots were taken after 1, 3, 7 min of reaction at 320°C.

Figure S7 TEM micrographs of aliquots of CdSe cores/CdTe arms with time: a) 1 min after injection b) 3 min after injection c) after 7 min d) 120 min after injection.

The CdSe/CdTe system showed the fastest grow rate. After 1 min of the reaction (Fig.6a) branches were very clearly seen, they were uneven in length at this particular stage however not longer than 50 nm. The further evolution of the multi-armed structures (Fig. S7b) and c)) increased the uniformity and as product of the synthesis multi-armed nanostructures with

uniform arm length (around 100 nm) were obtained (with arms growing only from 4 facets). If the reaction was run for for 2 hours (Fig. S7d), the arms were significantly shorter, and the multiple arms growing from the same facet had ripened into just one arm.

4.4.4 CdSe core/CdTe arms: Figure 6 shows the evolution of octapods with time. Aliquots were taken after 2, 4, 7 min of reaction at 350°C.

a)

b)

c)

Figure S8 TEM micrographs of aliquots of CdSe cores/CdTe arms with time: a) 1 min after injection b) 3 min after injection c) after 7 min d) 120 min after injection.

The same reaction conditions as in 4.4.3 with just the reaction temperature changed from 320°C to 350°C results also in multi-armed structures with tetrahedral symmetry after one minute. (figure S8a) . However, a lower number of arms per facet are formed than at lower temperature (in many cases only two arms per facet). Also in this case, the multiple arms on each facet coalesce into one single arm, but this process is already completed after just 7 minutes (figure S8c) instead of 2 hours as in the case of 320°C reaction temperature.

4.5 Synthesis at various temperatures

4.5.1 CdSe core /CdS arms - synthesis at 300°C (Fig.S9). Those conditions did not allow growth of the octapods.

Fig.S9 CdSe core /CdS arms - synthesis at 300°C

4.5.2 CdSe core /CdSe arms - synthesis at 280°C (Fig.S10). At lower temperatures the final product is a hyper-branched structure.

Figure S10 CdSe core /CdSe arms - synthesis at 280°C

4.5.3 CdSe core /CdTe arms - synthesis at 280°C (Fig.S11).The final product had similar shape but shorter arms as the nanoparticles synthesized at higher temperatures.

Fig.S11 CdSe core /CdTe arms - synthesis at 280°C.

4.5.4 CdSe core /CdS arms - at 380°C. Synthesis leads to transformation of octapods to tetrapods after longer reaction time.

a)

b)

Figure S12. CdSe core/CdS arms synthesis at 380°C. a) Products after 7 min of the reaction b) products after 6 hours of the reaction.

The final product of the synthesis after 6 hours (Fig. S12b) is a mixture of tetrapods and octapods. The transformation of octapods to tetrapods is clearly visible. However, in the case of CdSe/CdS octapods this transformation takes a long time even under these harsh conditions.

5 Elemental analysis. This was carried out via Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectroscopy on diluted solutions of nanocrystals. The samples were digested in HCl/HNO₃ 3:1 (v/v). In the case of the Cu_{2-x}Se seeds, elemental analysis was aimed at determining their concentration in solution, such that a known number of seeds was used in the synthesis of the multipods (see table 1). This was possible by combining information from TEM and from elemental analysis. First, the size of the nanocrystals was assessed via statistical analysis on transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images (see later). At this point the average number of atoms of one atomic species per tetrapod was determined by building a structural model of the nanocrystal with the same geometrical parameters as determined by TEM. This allowed to estimate the total concentration of a species, for example Selenium (Se), in the solution. By combining this information with the average number of Selenium (Se) atoms per individual nanocrystal (Se), it was possible to estimate the concentration of nanocrystals in the sample. Furthermore, elemental analysis showed that within the experimental error of the analysis, there was no Cu detected in the octapods synthesized by the “one-pot” approach.

6 Morphological, structural and compositional analysis by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Low-resolution TEM images were recorded on a JEOL JEM 1011 microscope operating at 100 kV. High resolution TEM (HRTEM) measurements and energy filtered images were performed with a JEOL JEM-2200FS microscope, equipped with a field

emission gun working at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV, a CEOS spherical aberration corrector and an Omega filter. Energy filtered images were acquired using a contrast aperture of about 10mrad to reduce aberrations (mostly chromatic). An elastic image (or zero/loss image) was acquired as a reference area with a 10eV energy slit. Chemical maps from Cu L (931eV) and Se L (1436eV) edges were obtained by acquiring three images (one post-edge and two pre-edge) respectively, to extract the background, with an energy slit of 50eV for Cu and 60eV for Se. The samples for TEM analysis were prepared in a glove box by depositing a few drops of a dilute solution of nanocrystals onto carbon-coated Cu grids. The latter were then transferred immediately into the microscope.

7 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). High resolution SEM images were recorded on a Raith150-TWO Electron Beam Lithography (EBL) system equipped with a thermal-field-emission source and a Gemini column.

8 Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD). XRD measurements were performed with a Rigaku SmartLab X-ray diffractometer. Concentrated nanocrystal solutions were spread on top of a silicon miscut substrate, after which the sample was allowed to dry and was then measured in parallel beam reflection geometry $\theta/2\theta$.

9 Optical absorption and emission spectroscopy. Optical absorption measurements were carried out using a Varian Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer. Nanocrystals were dispersed in toluene solution.